

The role of open data in driving innovation: insights from UniProt

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Purpose

This paper examines the long-term impact of open data in driving innovation, with a specific focus on the Universal Protein Resource (UniProt). The analysis was conducted within the framework of the Horizon Europe project – PathOS (under grant agreement No. 101058728) - which aims to develop and test a comprehensive framework for describing the impact pathways of open science. Indeed, the objective of analysis was to explore the long-term outcomes of UniProt in driving innovation outputs and enhancing academic productivity. Indeed, the availability of UniProt's open data, which can be integrated with proprietary datasets, may enable companies to accelerate innovation, resulting in increased patenting activities. At the same time academic researchers may leverage open biodata to generate new knowledge in life sciences, often resulting in a higher volume of research outputs, including publications.

Methods

To assess UniProt's contribution to knowledge production and innovation, a publication and a patent analysis was used to evaluate the influence of UniProt's data on the production of new knowledge, as embedded in new scientific publications and, ultimately, on innovations. The analysis involved retrieving data on scientific publications referencing UniProt or its resources from OpenAIRE, covering the period from 2003 to 2022 and data on patents referencing UniProt or its resources from Orbis IP, covering the period from 1988 to 2022. In other words, we searched for keywords in the title and abstract of scientific publications and in full text of patent publications, namely UniProt, Swiss-Prot, TrEMBL, UniProtKB, UniRef50, UniRef90, UniRef100, and UniParc. With reference to the patents mentioning UniProt and its resources, the analysis was expanded retrieving data on their patents, to capture the second wave of knowledge creation. The resulting database was analysed by means of text mining, i.e., use the SciNoBo algorithm to identify publications that contribute to UN SDG, and by means of descriptive statistics to investigate the research area and technological fields of the retrieved publications, their evolution over time, and the main authors or applicants. The analyses are carried out on the full database as well as disaggregated at UniProt resource level to identify specific patterns and characteristics at the resource level.

Results

The findings of the analyses conducted reveal the substantial impact of UniProt and its resources within both the scientific and intellectual property domains. UniProt has been mentioned in over 6,500 scientific publications and in more than 183 thousand patent publications, that belong to 44,747 distinct patent families. These figures highlight the extensive use of UniProt in both research and innovation. Furthermore, the data indicate a steady and significant increase in the number of publications and patents referencing UniProt over time. Specifically, the number of scientific publications citing UniProt has grown from 114 in 2003 to 515 in 2022, reflecting its expanding role in academic research. Similarly, the number of patent families mentioning UniProt has surged from just 5 in 1988 to an impressive 4,285 in 2022, demonstrating its growing importance in technological advancements and commercial applications. A closer examination of the publications citing UniProt shows that the majority reference UniProt as a whole (3,601 publications), Swiss-Prot (2,575 publications), and UniProtKB (1,119 publications). These publications predominantly belong to the field of medical and health sciences (4,117 publications), with a particular focus on developmental biology. Moreover, a substantial portion of these publications—1,962 (30.8%)—align with at least one United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (SDG), primarily SDG 3 ("Good Health and Well-being") and SDG 2 ("Zero Hunger"), underscoring the database's relevance in addressing global health and nutrition challenges. Similarly, an overwhelming majority of the patent families that reference UniProt also specifically mention Swiss-Prot and UniProt, emphasizing their foundational role in innovation. The vast majority—over 95%—of these patent families are intended to protect inventions within the chemistry sector, particularly in the fields of biotechnology (23,760 patent families, 54%) and pharmaceuticals (10,648 patent families, 25%), reflecting the database's crucial role in drug development and biotechnological research. In terms of geographic distribution, more than 60% of patent families were first filed with major intellectual property offices, including the United States Patent and Trademark Office (32.1%), the World Intellectual Property Organization (20.5%), and the European Patent Office (10.8%). Furthermore, 39% of patent families (17,459 in total) that reference UniProt resources have been cited by 137,363 subsequent patent publications, which belong to 76,082 distinct patent families, further demonstrating UniProt's role in knowledge dissemination and innovation development. These results demonstrate UniProt's significant contributions not only to advancing fundamental scientific knowledge but also to fostering practical applications.

Value

This study provides empirical evidence of the far-reaching impact of open data in driving innovation. By systematically analysing the contribution of UniProt to scientific and industrial advancements, it demonstrates the critical role of open-access resources in the knowledge economy. The findings support policies advocating for open data initiatives, emphasising their potential to foster interdisciplinary research, stimulate technological breakthroughs, and drive economic growth. The study also contributes to the broader discourse on open science by providing a methodological approach for assessing the impact pathways of publicly available datasets. Future research could further explore the mechanisms through which open data fosters collaboration, enhances research efficiency, and drives commercialisation.

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